

A NOTE ON THE ESTIMATION OF THIOSULPHATE

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Fogh (*Compt. rend.*, 1890, 110, 709 ; *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1890, vi, 21, 81) has reported that when silver nitrate is acted upon by sodium thiosulphate, silver thiosulphate is first formed. This product decomposes in presence of water to form silver sulphide as observed by Girard (*Ann. Chem. Anal. App.*, 1900, 5, 56). The reactions may be represented as follows :—

These facts have been utilised by us for the quantitative determination of sulphur in a solution of thiosulphate.

A solution of thiosulphate was prepared, and standardised with the aid of standard sodium arsenite and iodine solutions. To a measured volume of the thiosulphate solution was added drop by drop with constant stirring a solution of silver nitrate, till complete precipitation occurred. The colour of the precipitate was at first white, which soon changed to brick-red and finally to deep brown, probably due to the change of silver thiosulphate to silver sulphide. This precipitate was filtered in a Gooch crucible, washed thoroughly with water and the filtrate received in a beaker. The Gooch crucible was heated in an air-oven at 120° to a constant weight. The filtrate was concentrated to about 200 c.c., acidified slightly with nitric acid, boiled and a boiling solution of barium nitrate added drop by drop till barium sulphate precipitated completely. This was allowed to stand on a water-bath till the precipitate settled and the solution poured through a filter, the precipitate washed with hot water, filtered, dried, ignited and estimated as usual. The amount of sulphur contained in the precipitated silver sulphide and barium sulphate was calculated and thus the amount of total sulphur present in the solution known. It was found that the results obtained were fairly satisfactory, and the values lay within permissible error.

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